

Modeling of Needle Punched Nonwoven Structures to Analyse Porosity

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Abstract: This study presents a parametric model of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics developed using Python scripts and visualized through TexGen software. The model accurately represents the structural characteristics of needle punched nonwoven fabrics, considering parameters such as fiber diameter, orientation, fabric thickness, and areal density. Validation through porosity testing demonstrates the model's capability to replicate the complex microstructure of nonwoven fabrics. Additionally, the model can be exported in .IGES format for finite element method (FEM) analysis, enabling further exploration of mechanical properties.

Keywords: Nonwoven Modelling, Textile Modelling, 3D Modelling.

1 INTRODUCTION

The nonwoven fabrics are widely used for different purposes as filters, thermal and sound insulation and others. While developing non-woven fabric, many tests need to be carried out to determine its properties, and this creates a financial burden. Consequently, modeling nonwoven fabrics offers significant advantages in terms of convenience and efficiency in textile material development. Numerous models of nonwoven fabrics have been established to address this need; however, models specifically for needle-punched nonwoven fabrics remain limited [1], [2], [3], [4]. This study aims to fill this gap by creating a parametric model of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics at the fiber scale and employing this model in simulations.

The structural characteristics of nonwoven fabrics are primarily determined by factors such as fiber orientation, fiber diameter, fabric thickness, and areal density [5], [6], [7], [8]. Therefore, these parameters were considered and set as variables in the modeling process. In this model, fibers are represented as chains of cylinders that are randomly oriented, adhering to statistical distributions regarding their projection angles and vertical positions. The mathematical framework for this model is implemented using Python scripts, which ultimately visualize the structure through 3D modeling software, specifically TexGen. This approach not only provides a detailed and accurate representation of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics but also facilitates further simulations and analyses to optimize their properties for various applications.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Needle Punched Polyester Nonwoven

In this investigation, needle punched polyester nonwoven was chosen as the sample for modelling. The production process for the needle-punched polyester nonwoven fabric is detailed as follows.

To begin with, 50 grams of PET fibers were manually fed into a 337A Mesdan laboratory-type carding machine,

which is designed to create a single, uniform PET carded web. The carding machine's feeding conveyor belt has a width of 43 cm, while the end roller width is 48 cm, and it operates at a speed of 10 meters per minute. To achieve a homogeneous distribution of the fibers within the web, the initial carded web was taken from the end roller, rotated by 90 degrees, and fed back into the carding machine for a second pass.

Following the carding process, the needling process was conducted using a Cormatex S.R.L needle punching machine. This sophisticated machine is equipped with 2080 needles mounted on needle plates that span a width of 104 cm. During the needling process, notched needles were driven into the web from both the top and bottom at a 90-degree angle, ensuring thorough fiber entanglement and consolidation. This method effectively intertwines the fibers, resulting in a cohesive and robust needle-punched nonwoven fabric.

Table 1 presents the fundamental characteristics and specifications of the needle-punched polyester nonwoven fabric produced in this study. This comprehensive information provides a baseline understanding of the material properties, which is essential for subsequent modeling and simulation efforts.

Table 1 Characteristic of samples.

Name of Samples	Thickness (mm)	Areal Density (g/m ²)
Produced Nonwoven	4.15 ± 0.25	125

2.2 Determination of fiber's diameter in micron

The methodology employed to determine the diameter of fibers in the nonwoven fabric sample is described below. The measurement technique follows a standardized approach provided by MiniFIBERS Inc., which is effective for approximate fiber diameter estimation [9]. This method

hinges on the relationship between the fiber's fineness and the material density.

The diameter of a fiber (d_f) in microns can be calculated using the formula:

$$d_f [\mu\text{m}] = 11.89 * \sqrt{\frac{\text{fiber finenes [Den.]}}{\text{material density [g/mL]}}} \quad (1)$$

For polyester fibers, which are the focus of this study, the fineness is specified as 6.7 denier. The density of polyester is given as 1.38 g/mL. Substituting, these values into the formula, the fiber diameter is calculated as follows:

$$d_f [\mu\text{m}] = 11.89 * \sqrt{\frac{6.7 [\text{Den.}]}{1.38 [\text{g/mL}]}]} = 26.19 \mu\text{m} \quad (2)$$

Thus, the diameter of the polyester fiber is calculated to be approximately 26.19 microns. This calculated diameter is critical for nonwoven modeling, as it directly influences the properties of fabric.

2.3 Determination of number of fibers

The method described by Dabiryan et al. was utilized to determine the number of fibers in the nonwoven fabric sample [8]. In this study, the number of fibers was calculated following the same methodology. The areal density of the layers (M_F) was measured experimentally. For the given sample, the areal density is:

$$M_F = 125 \text{ g/m}^2 \quad (3)$$

The mass of each fiber can be calculated using the following relationship, which incorporates the fiber fineness:

$$m_f = L_f [m] \frac{F_f [\text{Den.}]}{9000} = 0.064 [m] \frac{6.7 [\text{Den.}]}{9000} = 4.764 \times 10^{-5} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the number of fibers per square meter of the fabric can be calculated as:

$$N_f = \frac{M_F}{m_f} = \frac{125 [\text{g/m}^2]}{4.764 \times 10^{-5} [\text{g}]} = 2\,623\,600 \left[\frac{1}{\text{m}^2}\right] \quad (5)$$

The number of fibers per square centimeter of the fabric in a single layer of the fabric is given by:

$$N_f = \frac{2\,623\,600 \left[\frac{1}{\text{m}^2}\right]}{10\,000} = 262.36 \left[\frac{1}{\text{cm}^2}\right] \approx 262 \left[\frac{1}{\text{cm}^2}\right] \quad (6)$$

These calculations demonstrate the process of determining the number of fibers in the nonwoven fabric model, providing a clear and quantitative understanding of the fiber distribution within the material. This information is essential for accurate modeling and analysis of the nonwoven fabric's properties, enabling the optimization of its structure for various applications.

2.4 Mathematical Modeling

In this study, a Python-based algorithm was developed to simulate the random distribution and orientation of fibers within a three-dimensional textile structure, utilizing the TexGen program for visualization. The algorithm's primary objective is to model the geometric properties of fibers and determine their arrangement within a fabric. This is achieved by defining random starting points and segments for each fiber, ensuring a realistic simulation of fiber placement. The details of the algorithm are elaborated below.

Firstly, the parameters including fiber diameter, number of fibers, fiber length, and the dimensions of the fabric were specified. Each fiber begins at a random starting point, with these coordinates chosen within the ranges $x_{start} \in [0, \text{width}]$, $y_{start} \in [0, \text{height}]$ and a thickness segment from the current z-position to 0.5 mm above it. The z-coordinate for each fiber is incremented by the step size in each iteration, ensuring a uniform distribution along the depth. The step size is determined by dividing the total number of fibers by the fabric's thickness.

The fibers are divided into segments of a specific length, which is calculated by dividing the total fiber length by the number of segments. The orientation of each segment is determined by a random angle uniformly distributed between 0 and 2π . This random orientation ensures that each fiber segment has a unique direction. The endpoints of these segments are calculated using the trigonometric relationships based on the segment length and angle:

$$L_{segment} = \frac{\text{Fiber Length}}{\text{Number of Segment}} \quad (7)$$

$$x_{segment} = x_{prev} + L_{segment} * \cos(\theta) \quad (8)$$

$$y_{segment} = y_{prev} + L_{segment} * \sin(\theta) \quad (9)$$

To ensure that the fiber segments remain within the fabric boundaries, adjustments are made if any segment exceeds these limits. For instance, if the x-coordinate of a segment is less than 0, it is set to 0. Similar corrections are applied for other boundary conditions, such as if the x-coordinate of a segment is greater than the width or if the y-coordinate is greater than the height.

Each fiber is defined as a yarn object, with node objects added to represent the starting and intermediate points. The fiber's shape is set to an elliptical form using section ellipse and assigned a constant section with yarn section constant. Finally, each fiber is added to the textile object. This Python-based algorithm, visualized using the TexGen program, provides a realistic simulation of the spatial arrangement and orientation of fibers within a textile structure, serving as a crucial tool for examining the microstructures of textile materials. The accuracy and efficacy of the algorithm can be further supported through advanced analyses and experimental validation.

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Visualization of Modeling

Based on the specified model parameters and methodology, a Python script was developed to facilitate the modeling process. This script generates a file containing the coordinates of all the fibers within the nonwoven fabric model. These coordinates are then visualized in three dimensions using the TexGen program, allowing for a comprehensive examination of the fiber arrangement.

The visualization produced by TexGen enables the model to be viewed from multiple perspectives, providing valuable insights into the structural characteristics and spatial distribution of the fibers. Additionally, the Python script is designed to be flexible, enabling adjustments to the model parameters to accommodate different types of fibers and fabric areal density. This adaptability ensures that the modeling approach can be applied to a wide range of needs punched nonwoven fabric types, enhancing its utility in both research and industrial applications.

Figure 1 Image of model from TexGen. The length of the model is 10x10x4.15 mm.

Overall, the integration of algorithmic modeling with advanced visualization techniques offers a powerful tool for the nonwoven fabrics. By providing a clear and detailed representation of the fiber structure, it supports the development of materials with tailored properties to meet specific application requirements.

3.2 Porosity Test Result

The porosity test results presented in this study highlight the effectiveness of the developed model in approximating the structural characteristics of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics. Using ImageJ software, the quantitative analysis of fiber fraction and porosity, as detailed in Table 2, indicates a strong correlation between the produced nonwoven sample and the model nonwoven sample. The SEM images illustrate the structural similarities between the produced and modeled nonwoven fabrics in Figure 2. The produced nonwoven sample exhibited a fiber fraction of 63.7% and a porosity of 36.3%, while the modeled nonwoven sample showed a fiber fraction of 61.4% and a porosity of 38.6%. The minor discrepancies of 2.3% in porosity are within acceptable limits, considering the

inherent variability of produced nonwoven structures and the simplifications made during the modeling process.

Figure 2 SEM images of produced nonwoven samples (a-b). Images of Modelling (c-d). Produced nonwoven image and model image is shown 3 mm x 3 mm. Fiber fraction and porosity analysis of produced nonwoven and model nonwoven were conducted in b and d, respectively. Scale bars are 1 mm.

Table 2 Fiber fraction and porosity values obtained from representative images of Produced Nonwoven and Model Nonwoven.

Name of Samples	Fiber Fraction (%)	Porosity (%)
Produced Nonwoven	63.7	36.3
Model Nonwoven	61.2	38.8

These results validate the modeling approach, demonstrating its capability to replicate the complex structure of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics with a high degree of accuracy. The close match between the experimental and modeled data suggests that the assumptions and parameters used in the model, such as fiber orientation, fiber diameter, fabric thickness, and areal density, are appropriately chosen and effectively implemented. In conclusion, the successful validation of the nonwoven fabric model through porosity testing underscores its potential as a valuable tool in textile material science. By providing accurate and detailed representations of nonwoven structures, this model facilitates a deeper understanding of material behavior and supports the development of high-performance nonwoven fabrics tailored to specific applications.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, a parametric model of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics was developed, aiming to provide a comprehensive understanding of their structural characteristics and porosity. The model, implemented using Python scripts and visualized through TexGen software, accurately represents the spatial arrangement and orientation of fibers within the fabric. By considering parameters such as fiber diameter, fiber orientation, fabric

thickness, and areal density, the model effectively simulates the complex microstructure of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics.

Validation of the model was conducted through porosity testing, comparing the results of the modeled nonwoven fabric with those of a produced nonwoven sample. The close agreement between the experimental and modeled data demonstrates the capability of the model to replicate the structural features of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics with high accuracy. The minor discrepancies observed in porosity values are within acceptable limits, considering the inherent variability of produced nonwoven structures.

Overall, the developed model offers a valuable tool for researchers and engineers in the textile industry to analyze and optimize the properties of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics. By providing a detailed understanding of their microstructure, the model facilitates the development of high-performance nonwoven materials tailored to specific applications, such as filters, thermal insulation, and soundproofing. Further research can explore the integration of this model with finite element method (FEM) analysis by exporting it in .IGES format through TexGen visualization. This integration would enable comprehensive simulations to analyze the mechanical properties and behavior of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics under various loading conditions.

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